

Deliverable D-JRP22

Workpackage WP5.5

Responsible Partner: ANSES

Contributing partners: ISS

GENERAL INFORMATION

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European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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	OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>	
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KICK-OFF ANNUAL MEETING of MEME PROJECT ORGANIZED by ANSES in NANCY (FRANCE)

1.1. MEME PROJECT

MEME (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-meme/>) is a multicentre collaborative international project (2020-2022) composed by 20 partners from 15 countries. MEME is aiming to fill the research gaps highlighted by international agencies for the detection and control of cystic and alveolar echinococcosis (CE and AE). MEME, expanding the results of previous European projects, will focus on both the standardization, harmonization and validation of existing parasitological and molecular methods, and the development and comparative assessment of innovative molecular tools and biomarkers to detect *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Em) and *Echinococcus granulosus s.l.* (Eg) in the food chain. A biomarker discovery task will also focus on the proteomic analysis of exosomes in sheep plasma, to develop innovative tools for the detection of CE the natural intermediate host. Production of epidemiological data on the presence of Em/Eg eggs in the food chain will focus on vegetables for human consumption as well as dogs' faeces in selected endemic countries. Moreover, food source-targeted questionnaires will be developed and administered to a sample of patients with CE, in selected hospitals, including those registered in the European Register of CE (ERCE), and AE and matched controls, to advance our knowledge on food-related risk factors for human infection. Organization and delivery of parasitological and molecular Proficiency Testing Schemes on the validated techniques will be organized.

Altogether, MEME will provide a comprehensive set of relevant integrative activities (including development and validation of protocols, collection of biological material, capacity building, and epidemiological investigations). These will allow partner organisations to harmonize procedures, improve detection of Eg and Em, and define control strategies based on the occurrence of these pathogens in the food chain and the relative importance of their food-borne transmission.

1.2 AGENDA of THE KICK-OFF MEETING HELD on 5-6 FEBRUARY in NANCY, FRANCE

Here we report all the activities launched and discussed during the 2 working days of MEME project.

DAY 1 (05/02/2019)

8:45 - 9:00 Registration (ANSES)

9:00 - 9:05 Welcome - Adriano Casulli (Project Coordinator, ISS) and Franck Boue (ANSES)

9:10 - 9:25 Introduction to One Health EJP (Casulli, ISS)

09:25 - 11:00 Consortium presentation (N=17)

- Presentation of ISS (funded partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Casulli) (5min)
- Presentation of FLI (funded partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Conraths) (5min)
- Presentation of ANSES (funded partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Boue) (5min)
- Presentation of RIVM (funded partner) and the Unit involved in the project (van der Giessen) (5min)
- Presentation of PIWET (funded partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Karamon) (5min)
- Presentation of SVA (funded partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Isaksson) (5min)
- Presentation of NVI (funded partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Davidson) (5min)
- Presentation of SSI (funded partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Jokelainen) (5min)
- Presentation of INIAV (funded partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Gomes) (5min)
- Presentation of INSA (funded partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Gargate) (5min)
- Presentation of UT (funded partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Saarma) (5min)
- Presentation of VFL (funded partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Moks) (5min)
- Presentation of BIOR (external partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Deksne) (5min)
- Presentation of UH (external partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Wassermann) (5min)
- Presentation of IPZ (external partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Deplazes) (5min)
- Presentation of LRUJ (external partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Al-Jawabreh) (5min)
- Presentation of TH (external partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Dvir) (5min)
- Presentation of IZSS (external partner) and the Unit involved in the project (Bonelli) (5min)

11:00 - 11:30 Coffee break

11:30 - 11:45 MEME project: overview and aims (Casulli, ISS)

11:45 - 13:00 WP1: SAMPLING STRATEGY [Short intro: Karamon, PIWET]

- T1. SOPs for sampling in matrices (Casulli, ISS) (5min)
- T2. Matrices collection in the field from intermediate/definitive hosts (Karamon, PIWET) (10min)
- T3. Matrices collection from experimental animal models
 - ST1. Mouse/fox model of Em (Boue, ANSES) (10min)
 - ST2. Sheep model of Eg (Gomes, INIAV) (5min)
- Discussion and tasks allocation (45min)

13:00 - 14:00 Lunch

14:00 - 15:30 WP2: VALIDATION of PARASITOLOGICAL and MOLECULAR ASSAYS [Short intro: Boue, ANSES]

- T1. Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique, SSCT (Boue, ANSES) (10min)
- T2. Comparison of multiplex PCRs (Casulli, ISS) (10min)
- T3. Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay (Isaksson, SVA) (10min)
- Discussion and tasks allocation (60min)

15:30 - 16:00 Coffee break

16:00 - 18:00 **WP3: DEVELOPMENT/VALIDATION of NEW TOOLS and PRODUCTION of DATA RELEVANT for EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENTS** [Short intro: [Maksimov, FLI](#)]

- **T1.** New molecular markers for Em and Eg sl (from rapid diagnostics to source attribution)
 - ST1.** New mitochondrial markers ([Saarma, UT](#)) (10min)
 - ST2.** New microsatellite markers ([Umhang, ANSES](#)) (10min)
 - ST3.** NGS-based method ([Saarma, UT](#)) (10min)
- **T2.** New multiplex TaqMan qPCR for detection and genotyping of Em/Eg ([Maksimov, FLI](#)) (10min)
- **T3.** Detection of Em/Eg in complex samples: sequencing using RSE/NGS ([Øines, NVI](#)) (10min)
- **T4.** Proteomic study on biomarker discovery in exosomes from animal plasma ([Casulli, ISS](#)) (10min)
- Discussion and tasks allocation (60min)

20:00 - Social dinner in Nancy (Organized by [ANSES](#))

DAY 2 (06/02/2019)

9:00 - 10:30 **WP3: DEVELOPMENT/VALIDATION of NEW TOOLS and PRODUCTION of DATA RELEVANT for EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENTS**

- **T5.** Assessment of new molecular methods *versus* the existing ones ([Maksimov, FLI](#)) (5min)
- **T6.** Contamination of vegetables for human consumption by Em/Eg ([Umhang, ANSES](#)) (10min)
- **T7.** Prevalence of Em/Eg in dogs (faecal samples) from selected areas ([Karamon, PIWET](#)) (10min)
- **T8.** Potential human risk factors for CE/AE by means of questionnaires ([Casulli, ISS](#)) (10min)
- **T9.** Eg genotype diversity in Northern Israel ([Dvir, TH](#)) and Palestine ([Al-Jawabreh, LRUJ](#)) (5+5min)
- Discussion and tasks allocation (45min)

11:00 - 11:30 Coffee break

11:30 - 13:00 **WP4: TRAINING, DISSEMINATION & PROFICIENCY TESTING SCHEMES** [Short intro: [Casulli, ISS](#)]

- **T1.** Trainings: 1) SSCT ([Umhang, ANSES](#)); 2) M-PCRs ([Maksimov, FLI](#)); 3) MC-RT-PCR ([Isaksson, SVA](#)); 4) RSE-NGS ([Øines, NVI](#)) (4x10min)
- **T2.** Dissemination of project results (Scientific publication policy) ([Casulli, ISS](#)) (10min)
- **T3.** PTs: 1) SSCT ([Boue, ANSES](#)) ; 2) M-PCRs ([Casulli, ISS](#)); 3) MC-RT-PCR ([Isaksson, SVA](#)); 4) RSE-NGS ([Jokelainen, SSI](#)) (4x5min)
- Discussion and tasks allocation (20min)

13:00 - 14:15 Lunch & [Consortium photo](#)

14:15 - 14:30 **Hints on administrative/financial aspects and project DEADLINES...** ([Casulli, ISS](#))

14:30 - 16:00 Roundtable on WPs and tasks

16:15 Conclusions and adjourn

1.3 LIST of PARTICIPANTS

NAME SURNAME	INSTITUTE	COUNTRY
FUNDED PARTNERS		
Vanessa Bastid	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety, ANSES	France
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Peter Deplazes	Institute of Parasitology, University of Zurich, IPZ	Switzerland
Eran Dvir	Tel Hai College, TH	Upper Galilee, Israel
Cinzia Santucci	Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Sardegna, IZSS	Italy
Marion Wassermann	University of Hohenheim, UH	Germany

Picture of the participants to the kick-off meeting of MEME project organized by ANSES in Nancy, France on 5-6 february 2020.